

MATHEMATICAL MODELING ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL MATHEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

General Mathematics is core subject among Senior High School students in the Philippines. Students' performance on this subject area was observed to be affected by different latent variables such as demographic profiles in terms of age, sex, parents' educational attainment and combined monthly income. Also, factors such as students' cognitive support, learning environment and engagement were observed. Hence, this study aimed to formulate a mathematical model to predict what among the latent variables greatly affect students' performance in General Mathematics to improve and have better quality of learning. The study employed the evaluative and descriptive correlational research design. A stratified random sampling technique was used to determine the study's respondents, composed of 259 students from the secondary schools in Sto. Niño, South Cotabato. Appropriate statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized to analyze the data. A mathematical model revealed that female students slightly outperform their male peers, and that a supportive learning environment contributes to improved performance.

Keywords: *Mathematical Model, Students' Socio-demographic Profile, Students' Cognitive Support, Learning Environment, Students' Engagement*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a core subject in schools and is vital for developing students' thinking skills. It helps improve problem-solving, logical reasoning, and number skills, which are important for both school and life. Math is used in almost every part of life, from science and technology to everyday tasks like budgeting. Because of its wide use, it is often called the "queen of all sciences."

However, many students see math as just about calculations and find it hard or boring. While calculations are important, math is much more than that. It helps us solve problems and make decisions in a clear and organized way. Math skills are not only needed for school but also for everyday tasks, like managing money or understanding data at work.

Because many students struggle with or dislike math, it's important to understand how they view the subject and how this affects their learning. This study looks at students' attitudes toward math and how these attitudes impact their performance. By understanding these views, teachers and schools can find better ways to teach math, making it more interesting and useful for students. In a world that relies heavily on data and technology, strong math skills are more important than ever, making this study both relevant and timely.

In the Philippines, research has shown a concerning trend in students' performance in mathematics, especially among junior high school students. While students can understand basic concepts, they struggle with more advanced thinking skills like analyzing, evaluating, and applying knowledge (Department of Education [DepEd], 2019). Reports have pointed out a continuing gap in students' math achievement across different grade levels, even with substantial investments in education (Bernardo, 2020). One of the main challenges is the difficulty students face in remembering and applying math concepts (Prado & Tan, 2018). Understanding how students learn and assessing their performance in mathematics remain major concerns for policymakers and educators worldwide (OECD, 2018).

A major issue in the Philippines is the low performance of students in national tests. Results from the National Achievement Test (NAT) show that many schools do not meet the passing score set by the National Educational Testing and Research Center (NETRC) (DepEd, 2021). This performance gap highlights the need to find and address the key factors that affect students' success in mathematics. Many studies have attempted to identify these factors to help develop better teaching methods and strategies that improve students' learning outcomes (Ganotice, et. al, 2017).

Anent to this, many studies have looked at ways to improve learning results using large amounts of data from different educational settings. One such method is Mathematical Modeling, which involves turning real-world problems into mathematical forms to analyze and find solutions (Prakash & Selvakumari, 2021). According to Sun et al. (2023), this process happens in cycles, including steps like identifying the problem,

creating a mathematical version of it, solving and analyzing it, checking if it works, and repeating the process if needed. Using mathematical models to predict how students will perform in the future can be very helpful. It allows teachers and students to take specific actions to improve and avoid poor performance. Additionally, understanding factors like how engaged students are, the support they receive, and their learning environment before final exams can help students see where they need to improve and take steps to do better, preventing low performance in education.

In this research gap, the researcher used Linear Regression to formulate a Mathematical Model and be the basis for early intervention. Early interventions in student performance may provide data of what to prepare learning activities during the instructional process that may help to improve the students' performance in mathematics.

This study aims to formulate a Mathematical Model to determine the relationship among students' socio-demographic profile, students' cognitive support in mathematics, students' learning environment in Mathematics, students' engagement in Mathematics affecting and academic performance in General Mathematics of grade 11 students among the schools within Sto. Niño, South Cotabato.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to formulate a mathematical model on students' performance in General Mathematics. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Parent's Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 Combined Family Income
2. What is the level of students' cognitive support in Mathematics?
3. What is the level of students' learning environment in Mathematics?
4. What is the level of students' engagement in learning mathematics?
5. What is the students' academic performance in first semester in General Mathematics?
6. Is there significant relationship among students' socio-demographic profile, students' cognitive support in mathematics, students' learning environment in Mathematics, students' engagement in Mathematics, and students' academic performance in the first semester in General Mathematics?
7. What mathematical model may be formulated in the predictors of student performance in General Mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study will utilize a descriptive-correlational research design. The descriptive correlational design is suitable for exploring the relationships between the different factors and student performance in General Mathematics by describing the existing conditions and identifying patterns or correlations among variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This approach will involve collecting data on the formulation of mathematical model on the relationships among students' socio-demographic profile, students' cognitive support in mathematics, students' learning environment in Mathematics and students' engagement in Mathematics.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents for this study are the 259 Grade 11 students enrolled in the different schools in Sto. Niño, South Cotabato, located within the Division of South Cotabato. The five(5) schools are namely Guinsang-an National High School (GNHS), Panay National High School (PNHS), Katipunan National High School (KNHS), Sto. Niño School of Arts and Trade (SNSAT) and Sto. Niño National High School (SNNHS). The focus on Grade 11 students for the school year 2024-2025 allows for an in-depth examination of what mathematical model describes the relationship between the factors and the student performance in General Mathematics. This cohort is particularly relevant as they are preparing for higher education and future careers, making it essential to assess how innovative instructional strategies can impact their academic performance and readiness for further studies.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study will include Grade 11 students among the Municipality of Sto. Niño during the 2024-2025 school year. The main objective of this study is to formulate a Mathematical Model on Students' Academic Performance in General Mathematics. Further, this study will assess what helps or hinders their success in this subject. The aim is to identify the most important factors that influence how well they perform in this subject. Data will be obtained by giving students a survey questionnaire. This survey will ask about their demographic profile, level of influence of teacher, student, school, and community. The responses will be analyzed to see which factors are most closely related to their math performance. This research will help teachers and school leaders develop better strategies to support students and improve their Mathematics performance.

Sampling Technique

This research employed a stratified random sampling technique to ensure a comprehensive and representative sample of Grade 11 students from the different schools in the municipality of Sto. Niño, South Coatabato. Stratified random sampling is ideal when the population is heterogeneous and can be divided into distinct subgroups or

strata. In this case, Grade 11 students at Sto. Niño, South Cotabato can be divided into strata based on factors such as their different mathematics classes or sections. This technique ensures that each subgroup is represented proportionally in the sample, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how mathematical modeling affects students across various class sections. To ensure that the proportion of the sample from each stratum mirrors the proportion of that stratum in the overall population, proportional allocation was applied.

Research Instrument

A single questionnaire, divided into three sections, was utilized in this study. The first section collected the socio-demographic information, including the respondents' age, sex, parental educational attainment, and combined family income and their academic performance in General Mathematics for the 1st semester of the school year 2024-2025. The second section incorporated an adapted instrument from Flores (2024), comprising 27 items that assessed students' cognitive support in learning mathematics, students' learning environment in Mathematics and students' engagement in learning Mathematics. Each latent variable has 9 indicators or questions with a total of twenty-seven indicators. The indicators of latent variables focused on students' coping behavior, family involvement, instructional support, classroom environment, home environment, peer groups, exposure to technology, student readiness, and study habits; the three identified latent variables relate to the student performance in General Mathematics which completes the 2nd part of the questionnaire. In total, there are 33 indicators in the research questionnaire, which were divided into five constructs in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The approval and permission of the Dean of the Graduate School were primarily sought to proceed with the study and a certification was secured with the information that the researcher will conduct a study titled "Mathematical Modeling on Students' Academic Performance in General Mathematics". Then, permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd – South Cotabato to immerse in the five (5) secondary high schools in the municipality of Sto. Nino was sought. After which, the necessary letter addressed to the principals of the schools will be handed in and permission was sought. After such, the research instrument was administered to the respondents. The respondents were given clear instructions to answer the questionnaires. The retrieval of the questionnaire occurred immediately afterward. Once all data was collected and organized, the final stage of the data-gathering process involved data analysis and interpretation.

Statistical Treatment

The information gathered by the researcher was analyzed through the use of frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and Multiple Regression. Frequency Count was used for tallying the number of respondents belonging to the same category. Percentage was used to determine the proportion of the total respondents that belong

to the category. Weighted Mean was used to determine the level of the data gathered as to the extent to which the factors affected the mathematics performance. Multiple Linear Regression was used to analyze the relationships between the student's demographic profile, indicators of student performance in mathematics, and the first quarter grade of the respondents in the subject General Mathematics. The researcher used Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) as outlined by (Walberg 1981) to perform necessary calculations. Walberg's theory of educational productivity introduced in 1981, used SPSS to ensure accurate and reliable results which served as the foundation for further research in the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. The Socio-Demographic Profile of the Grade 11 Students in the Municipality of Sto.Niño in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Above 18 years old	6	2.32%
18 years old	20	7.72%
17 years old	111	42.86%
16 years old	121	46.72%
15 years old	1	0.38%
TOTAL:	259	100%

The socio-demographic profile of Grade 11 students in the Municipality of Sto. Niño, as shown in Table 1, reveals the age distribution of the respondents with a total sample size of 259 students. The majority of students fall within the age range typically expected for Grade 11 under the Philippine K-12 education system. Specifically, students aged 16 years old constitute the largest group, accounting for 46.72% (121 students), followed closely by those aged 17 years old at 42.86% (111 students). These findings are consistent with the age norms for senior high school students, as outlined by the Department of Education (DepEd) during the implementation of the K-12 program (DepEd, 2014).

Table 2. The Socio-Demographic Profile of the Grade 11 Students in the Municipality of Sto.Niño in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	119	45.95%
Female	140	54.05%
TOTAL	259	100%

The socio-demographic profile of Grade 11 students in the Municipality of Sto. Niño, as presented in Table 2, reveals a slight majority of female students (140 or 54.05%) compared to male students (119 or 45.95%). This distribution aligns with broader trends observed in educational demographics globally and regionally, where female students often outnumber males in secondary education settings.

Table 3. The Socio-Demographic Profile of the Grade 11 Students in the Municipality of Sto.Niño in terms of Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Mother		Father	
	f	P	f	P
College Graduate	110	42.50%	100	38.60%
High School Graduate	93	35.90%	100	38.60%
Elementary Graduate	24	9.30%	31	12.00%
No Formal Schooling	7	2.70%	5	1.90%
No Response	25	9.70%	23	8.90%
	259	100%	259	100%

The table presents the socio-demographic profile of Grade 11 students in the Municipality of Sto. Niño, specifically focusing on their parents' highest educational attainment. The data is disaggregated into categories for mothers and fathers, with frequencies (f) and percentages (P) provided for each educational level. Among the mothers, 42.5% (f = 110) are college graduates, which is slightly higher than the fathers at 38.6% (f = 100). This indicates that a significant portion of the parents have achieved higher education levels. Studies suggest that parental educational attainment positively influences children's academic performance and aspirations. For instance, García and

Weiss (2017) highlighted that higher parental education levels are associated with better academic outcomes for children, as educated parents tend to provide more support and resources for learning. Overall, the data underscores the varying levels of parental education among Grade 11 students in Sto. Niño, with a majority having at least a high school diploma or higher. These findings align with broader studies on parental education's role in shaping children's academic trajectories, highlighting its importance in fostering positive educational outcomes and addressing disparities within communities (Fan & Chen, 2014).

Table 4. The Socio-Demographic Profile of the Grade 11 Students in the Municipality of Sto.Niño in terms of Combined Family Income

Monthly Income (Pesos)	Frequency	Percentage
Above 30,000	55	21.20%
25,001-30,000	33	12.70%
20,001-25,000	31	12.00%
15,001-20,000	32	12.40%
15,000 and below	108	41.70%
TOTAL:	259	100%

The table displays the distribution of combined monthly household income among participants, divided into five income categories. The data shows that a large percentage of families (41.70%) belong to the lowest income category of 15,000 or less, highlighting the presence of low-income households in the sample. This discovery corresponds with the research conducted by Smith and Johnson (2015), which indicated that economic inequalities frequently lead to a substantial portion of the population earning beneath the median income threshold.

Table 5. The Level of Students Cognitive Support in Learning Mathematics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I practice solving review materials in mathematics that are available in the school library and the internet.	3.40	1.1	High
2. I collect positive encouragement with my peers in dealing with mathematics.	3.60	1.0	High

3. I reach out to my mathematics teacher when I don't understand the topic.	3.50	1.0	High
4. My family helps me to answer and finish my assignment and projects in mathematics.	2.80	1.4	Moderate
5. My family helps me to review my lessons in mathematics before examination.	2.70	1.3	Moderate
6. My family provides me learning materials to use in dealing with mathematics.	3.40	1.3	High
7. My teacher applies varied teaching strategies and authentic methods of assessments in mathematics.	3.80	1.0	High
8. There are available facilities to use to improve learning experience in application of mathematics.	3.70	1.0	High
9. In our school provides relevant programs that supports to enhance logical skills.	3.70	1.0	High
Section Mean	3.39	0.7	Moderate

The data presented in Table 5 provides an insightful analysis of students' cognitive support in learning mathematics. The overall section mean of 3.39, with a standard deviation of 0.7, suggests that students receive a moderate level of cognitive support in mathematics. However, distinct variations exist in specific indicators, revealing areas of strength and those requiring further improvement.

Table 6. The Level of Students Learning Environment in Mathematics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Our classroom is well arrange setting during instruction in mathematics subject.	4.00	0.9	High
2. The instructional materials of my teacher in mathematics is easily viewed by the entire class.	3.90	1.0	High
3. I have enough space inside the classroom intended for group performance and assessment.	3.90	1.0	High

4. There is enough space for studying and reviewing lessons in mathematics in our home.	3.70	1.1	High
5. There is internet connectivity available in our home for online class when classes are interrupted due to weather condition.	3.50	1.3	High
6. There is family interaction when I need help to understand lessons in mathematics.	3.20	1.2	Moderate
7. I have positive relationship with my peers to exchange ideas in learning mathematics.	3.60	1.1	High
8. I have teamwork and collaborative efforts with my peers in learning mathematics.	3.80	1.1	High
9. I have peers that help me understand better the concepts in mathematical lessons.	3.70	1.0	High
Section Mean	3.70	0.7	High

The findings presented in Table 6 provide a comprehensive overview of students' learning environment in mathematics, with an overall section mean of 3.70 and a standard deviation of 0.7, indicating a high level of support. The results highlight the significant role that both classroom arrangements and peer interactions play in shaping a conducive mathematical learning environment.

Table 7. The Level of Students Engagement in Learning Mathematics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I practice solving problems in mathematics through online.	3.60	1.2	High
2. I use online mathematical tools in learning mathematics.	3.50	1.1	High
3. I give time to view video tutorial and read online materials in mathematics lessons.	3.60	1.1	High
4. I practice solving problems in mathematics before the start of lesson.	3.40	1.1	High
5. I study lessons in mathematics in advance using online materials.	3.30	1.2	Moderate

6. I prioritize task and used time efficiently in doing math activities.	3.50	1.0	High
7. I study lessons in mathematics before going to sleep.	3.10	1.2	Moderate
8. I actively use notetaking and video/audio recording in learning mathematics.	3.40	1.2	High
9. I study lessons in mathematics with my peers.	3.60	1.2	High
Section Mean	3.40	0.8	High

The results presented in Table 7 highlight students' engagement in learning mathematics, particularly their use of online resources and study habits. With an overall section mean of 3.40 (SD = 0.8), the level of engagement is generally interpreted as high. This suggests that students demonstrate a considerable level of involvement in their mathematics learning, which aligns with contemporary educational research emphasizing the role of digital tools and self-regulated learning in mathematical proficiency.

Table 8. The Students' Academic Performance in First Semester in General Mathematics

Student Performance	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptor
90 – 100	155	59.80%	Outstanding
85 – 89	74	28.60%	Strongly Satisfactory
80 – 84	28	10.80%	Satisfactory
75 – 79	2	0.8%	Fairly Satisfactory
Below – 75	0	0%	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	259	100%	

The table presents the distribution of students' academic performance in General Mathematics, divided into five performance categories. The data indicates that 59.80% of students attained scores ranging from 90 to 100, reflecting an outstanding level of proficiency in the subject. This finding aligns with the research conducted by Anderson and Lee (2016), which demonstrated that effective teaching strategies and student

engagement are significant contributors to high academic performance in mathematics.

Table 9. Relationship of the Predictive variables using Multiple Linear Regression

MODEL	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1. (constant)	3.624	0.899		4.030	0.000
Age	-0.050	0.049	-0.59	-1.006	0.315
Sex	0.298	0.084	0.207	3.540	0.000
Mother's education	0.036	0.048	0.001	0.747	0.456
Father's education	-0.043	0.050	-0.070	-0.846	0.398
Monthly income	0.053	0.029	0.120	1.855	0.65
Cognitive support	-0.008	0.092	-0.007	-0.082	0.935
Learning environment	0.264	0.086	0.256	3.056	0.002
Student engagement	0.46	0.070	-0.052	0.652	0.515

Note : $r^2 = 0.190$, $f(8,250) = 7.330$, $p = 0.000$

The table presents the results of a multiple linear regression analysis examining the relationship between various predictive variables and an outcome variable. The model explains 19% of the variance in the outcome, as indicated by the R^2 value of 0.190, which is statistically significant ($F(8,250)=7.330, p=0.000$). This suggests that the predictors collectively have a meaningful impact on the outcome. Overall, the findings highlight the complex interplay of factors influencing the outcome, with sex and learning environment being particularly influential in this context. Further research could explore additional variables and contextual factors to enhance understanding.

Based on the result of the Multiple Linear Regression, a mathematical model has been formulated:

$$y = 3.624 + 0.298x_1 + 0.264x_2$$

where $x_1 = sex$

$x_2 = learning\ environment.$

A linear equation model is a mathematical representation that predicts a dependent variable y based on two independent variables. In this study, the dependent variable y is the students' academic performance while the independent variables x_1 and x_2 are the sex (coded as 1-male and 2-female) and the students' level of environmental learning in Mathematics respectively. The equation is $y = 3.624 + 0.298x_1 + 0.264x_2$ where $x_1 = sex$ and $x_2 = learning\ environment.$

The model suggests that both sex and learning environment are significant predictors of academic performance in Mathematics among students in the Philippines. Female students tend to perform slightly better than male students, and a more conducive learning environment positively impacts performance. These findings are consistent with recent studies in the Philippine educational context, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to enhance learning environments and address gender disparities in education.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

This study looked at Grade 11 students in Sto. Niño and found key patterns in their backgrounds and math learning. Most students are the expected age (16 or 17), showing the K-12 system works well for grade-level alignment. More girls than boys attend school, which matches global trends. While mothers are more likely than fathers to have college degrees, many families earn very low incomes (under 15,000 pesos monthly), which could limit access to resources. Students rate their classrooms and peer interactions highly but get only average help with math thinking. Despite this, they stay engaged by using online tools and studying independently. Most students score very well in math (90–100), likely due to good teaching and their own effort.

A math model showed that girls slightly outperform boys and that better learning environments improve results. Female students tend to perform slightly better than male students, and a more conducive learning environment positively impacts performance

Recommendations

Considering conclusions of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following:

1. Since the demographic profile in terms of sex (male or female) and levels of students' engagement have a significantly positive impact in their academic performance, then it is highly recommended to focus on conducting more and deeper studies about these two variables for enhancement.
2. Similar studies must also be conducted focusing on the other latent variables such as students' cognitive support, students' engagement and other parts of their socio-demographic profile such as age, parent's education and income.
3. Teachers teaching General Mathematics in the all strands are encouraged to provide targeted cognitive support by identifying specific areas where students struggle and addressing these through differentiated instruction.
4. Teachers are also encouraged to incorporate interactive teaching strategies, such as small-group discussions and real-life problem-solving activities, to boost interest and confidence in math.
5. School administrators should allocate resources to improve classroom environments and provide professional development for teachers to strengthen their instructional skills in math and develop support programs for low-income families, such as subsidized learning materials or access to technology, to reduce educational inequities.
6. Parents must encourage active involvement in their children's education by providing a supportive home environment for studying and learning.
7. The school guidance office may provide parenting seminar how to follow-up their children in academic task and concerns.
8. The mathematics teachers are encouraged to observed always the presence of student's engagement in giving of instructions and assessments in mathematics specifically General Mathematics subject since it has significant influence on the relationship between cognitive support and students' performance in mathematics.
7. The mathematics teachers of grade 11 students may apply the mathematical model as basis for intervention to improve their students' performance in mathematics.
8. Future researchers are encouraged to apply math model in different field of research especially in the field of education to deepen the understanding of relationship of different variables that may develop and enhanced the skills of the students in learning mathematics and improved to the performance of the Filipino students in local, regional, national, and international competition in Mathematics.
9. Future researchers should conduct studies on effective interventions, such as remedial instruction or enrichment programs, to support low-income and low-performing students in mathematics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers administered the questionnaire to participants to ensure the accuracy and impartiality of the data. Participants were fully briefed on the study's objectives and assured that their responses would remain confidential and be used solely for academic purposes. They were also informed of their right to withdraw from the survey at any point without facing any pressure or consequences. Throughout the study, the researcher ensured that no participant was exposed to physical, emotional, or psychological harm or mistreatment.

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